

Molecules to materials : Platinum group metals organochalcogenolates to metal chalcogenides

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Manuscript received 16 May 2000

Platinum group metals chalcogenides (M_xE_y ; E = S, Se, Te) are of much current interest due to their relevance in catalysis and in semiconductor devices and related materials. To develop an efficient low temperature preparations of these materials, metal organochalcogenolates as potential molecular precursors have been studied. Thus a variety of palladium and platinum organochalcogenolates, such as $[M(\text{SeBz})_2(\text{PR}_3)_2]$, $[M_2\text{Cl}_2(\mu\text{-X})(\mu\text{-SeBz})(\text{PR}_3)_2]$, $[M_3(\mu\text{-E})_2(\text{PR}_3)_2\text{L}_2]$, $[\text{Pd}(\text{Epy})\{\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2(\text{PR}_3)\}]$, $[\text{Pd}_2(\mu\text{-ER})_2(\eta^3\text{-C}_4\text{H}_7)_2]$, etc. (M = Pd or Pt; E = S, Se or Te) have been prepared. They have been characterized by elemental analysis, NMR (^1H , ^{31}P , ^{77}Se , ^{195}Pt) and in some cases by X-ray diffraction. The thermal behaviour of these complexes has been studied by TGA.

Platinum group metal chalcogenides (M_xE_y ; M = platinum group metal; E = S, Se, Te) find extensive applications in catalysis¹⁻⁴ and materials science⁵⁻⁸. Examples of the latter include manufacture of semiconductors, solar cells⁵, high resolution lithographic films/plates⁶, optical disc recording films⁷, etc. The continuing drive for scaling down of these device dimensions has motivated research in design and development of organometallic precursor chemistry. This has led to an ever increasing number of organometallic precursor molecules which show lower growth temperatures and cleaner depositions.

Existing technologies to form small structures (referred as nano-scale structures) employ a 'top-down' approach where nano-structures are fabricated by reduction of large ones. Conversely, nano-devices can also be constructed from their atomic or molecular constituents, a methodology referred as 'bottom-up' approach. Although the bottom-up approach or 'retero-synthesis' technique is routinely employed in organic synthesis, this approach for inorganic materials (known or unknown) does not work. In the preparative solid state inorganic chemistry, it is neither possible to predict whether a particular structure would exist nor to design a new structural motif. To accomplish the task of retero-synthesis one has to consider various levels of hierarchical structure of molecular chemistry. As we move from molecules to solids, the number of possible arrangements of simple building blocks, such as coordination polyhedra into a regular three-dimensional structures appear to be limitless. These two approaches are pictorially depicted in Fig. 1. The figure shows progression in particle size from single atom, through clusters (with metal core size 1 nm),

Fig. 1. Progression of particle size from molecules to materials

nano-particles (with size upto 100 nm) leading to colloid and finally to the bulk material. These thematic ideas have been guiding our research for quite some time. Some of our results are described here.

Mononuclear complexes

Reaction of $[MCl_2(L-L)]$ with mercaptans in the presence of triethylamine readily gives mononuclear complexes $[M(SR')_2(L-L)]$. The selenolato and telluroolato complexes have been obtained by the reaction of $[MCl_2(L-L)]$ with sodium salt of organochalcogenolates in benzene-methanol mixture. The selenolato platinum complex can be obtained by oxidative addition of diphenyldiselenide on a platinum(0) complex (Scheme 1)⁹⁻¹².

Scheme 1

These complexes with monodentate phosphine ligands are usually formed as the *trans*-product, but in certain cases *cis*-derivatives can also be isolated which slowly isomerize to the *trans*-form. The complexes with chelating phosphines (dpmm, dppe, dppp), as expected, adopt a *cis*-configuration. The ³¹P NMR spectra exhibit a single resonance which is shielded relative to the corresponding dichloride. The resonance showed chalcogen dependence with shielding as S is replaced by Se and then Te. However, this trend is less prominent in the corresponding platinum complexes. The spectra of the latter are flanked with ¹⁹⁵Pt satellites. The magnitude of ¹J(Pt-P) is reduced significantly as compared with the corresponding dichlorides, reflecting high *trans*-influence of the ER' groups. Since the *trans*-influences for tertiary phosphines and organochalcogenides are comparable, the ¹J(Pt-P) values are expected to have similar magnitudes for the *cis*- and *trans*-isomers in the case of monodentate phosphine complexes. This observation poses difficulties in unambiguous identification of isomers formed for the thiolato complexes. However, both ⁷⁷Se and ¹²⁵Te nuclei have naturally occurring NMR active isotopes and hence the magnitude of ²J(⁷⁷Se/¹²⁵Te-³¹P) would enable identification of which isomer is formed. Thus the ³¹P NMR spectra of the complexes showing such couplings have been characterized

as *cis*-complexes. The ¹J(Pt-P) values are highly dependent on the nature of PR₃, E and R' groups. The magnitude of ¹J(Pt-P) increases in the following order of PR₃, E and R' ligands keeping other groups unchanged :

The ⁷⁷Se{¹H} NMR spectra of several complexes have been recorded. The *cis*-complexes showed doublets while for the *trans*-product triplet is observed. In the case of platinum complexes ²J(Se-P)_{cis} are small (~7 Hz). These complexes also showed platinum satellites [¹J(Pt-Se) = 100-160 Hz] (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. ⁷⁷Se{¹H} NMR spectra of (A) *trans*-[Pt(SePh)₂(PBu₃)₂] and (B) *cis*-[Pt(SePh)₂(dppe)] in CDCl₃

The ¹⁹⁵Pt{¹H} NMR spectra exhibited a triplet in the range δ -4035 to -5310 ppm due to coupling with phosphorus nuclei (Fig. 3). The ¹⁹⁵Pt NMR resonances are shielded on substituting dpmm for dppe. For dppe and monodentate phosphine complexes resonances appear in a

Fig. 3. ¹⁹⁵Pt{¹H} NMR spectrum of *cis*-[Pt(SePh)₂(dppe)] in CDCl₃

narrow range. The signal is shielded as sulfur is substituted for selenium and then tellurium, a trend in accord with the binding ability of the chalcogenide group (i.e. $SR' < SeR' < TeR'$).

Structures of $[Pt(SePh)_2(PPh_3)_2]$, $[Pd(SC_6F_5)_2(dppe)]$, $[Pd(SePh)_2(dppe)]$ and $[Pt(SePh)_2(dppm)]$ have been established by X-ray diffraction methods. The metal atoms in these molecules adopt a distorted square-planar configuration defined by two chalcogen atoms and two phosphorus atoms.

Dithiophosphate complexes

Dithiophosphate complexes are known to cleave cleanly and give sulfide derivatives. Thus the chemistry of platinum group metals dithiophosphate complexes has been investigated. Several molecules have been synthesized and characterized¹³⁻²⁴.

Trimethylplatinum(IV) complexes :

Trimethylplatinum(IV) complexes such as $PtMe_3Cp$, $[PtMe_3(\beta\text{-dik})_2]$, etc. have been employed as molecular precursors to deposit platinum films. The trimethylplatinum(IV) dithio complexes may serve as precursors for the preparation of platinum sulfide. Thus several trimethylplatinum dithiophosphate complexes have been isolated and characterized (Scheme 2). These complexes have been character-

Scheme 2

ized by 1H , ^{31}P and ^{195}Pt NMR spectroscopy^{13,14}. The ^{195}Pt NMR spectrum of $[PtMe_3(S_2PPh_2)]_2$ displayed a triplet at

$\delta -2592$ ppm with $^2J(Pt-P)$ 66 Hz suggesting a dimeric structure. The ^{195}Pt NMR spectrum of $[PtMe_3(S_2PPh_2)(py)]$ exhibited a doublet at $\delta -2632$ ppm with $^2J(Pt-P)$ 63 Hz, indicating its monomeric nature. The magnitude of $^2J(Pt-P)$ for these complexes has been of the order of 56–83 Hz (from ^{31}P NMR). Various modes of bonding of ligand has been demonstrated in these complexes, which is also the trend for ^{31}P NMR signal deshielding : tridentate < bidentate < monodentate < ionic. Structures of $[PtMe_3(S_2PPh_2)]_2$ and $[PtMe_3(S_2PPh_2)py]$ has been established by X-ray crystallography. In the former, the dithio ligand is attached to two platinum atoms giving rise to tri-connective bridges. Each platinum atom is coordinated by three *fac*-methyl groups and three *fac*-sulfur atoms. The two phosphinic acid ligands are mutually *cis* to the four-membered Pt_2S_2 ring. The structure of $[PtMe_3(S_2PPh_2)(py)]$ consists of discrete monomeric molecule. The dithio ligand is symmetrically chelated¹⁴.

Organopalladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes :

Organopalladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes¹⁵⁻¹⁹ have been isolated by substitution of halide with a dithio ligand (Scheme 3). Both mono- and binuclear precursors

Scheme 3

can be used, in each case only mononuclear complexes formed with chelated dithio ligand. The dithio-ligand strongly bonds with metal atom and does not cleave by addition of a phosphine ligand. This is in contrast to the complexes containing a halide or thio ligand. Structure of $[PtMe\{S_2P(OPr^i)_2\}(AsPh_3)]$ has been determined. The dithiophosphate ligand is asymmetrically chelated. The Pt-S distance 2.434(2) Å *trans* to the methyl group is longer than that [2.341(2) Å] *trans* to triphenylarsine. The four-membered PtS_2P ring is planar which is coplanar with the square plane of the platinum atom.

Ortho-metallated palladium(II) complexes have also been isolated and characterized (Equation 1). Structure of $[Pd\{S_2P(OPr^n)_2\}(NMe_2CH_2C_6H_4)]$ has been established by

 Fig. 5. $^{31}\text{P}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{PPr}_3)(\text{Sepy})\text{PtCl}(\text{PPr}_3)]$.

a single resonance which is deshielded from the corresponding signal for the respective mononuclear complex. Similarly, deshielding was observed for the ^{195}Pt NMR signals. For example, the ^{195}Pt resonances for $[\text{Pt}(\text{SePh})_2(\text{dppe})]$ and $[\text{Pt}_2(\mu\text{-SePh})_2(\text{dppe})_2][\text{BPh}_4]_2$ appear at δ -4975 and -4544 ppm, respectively. The presence of $^3J(\text{Pt-P})$ (~30 Hz) in ^{31}P NMR spectra and $^2J(\text{Pt-Pt})$ (~650 Hz) in ^{195}Pt NMR spectra indicates the formation of binuclear complexes (Fig. 6).

 Fig. 6. $^{31}\text{P}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $[\text{Pt}_2(\mu\text{-SePh})_2(\text{dppm})_2][\text{BPh}_4]_2$ in CDCl_3 .

Several binuclear organochalcogenolate-bridged complexes can be isolated from binuclear precursors. Benzylselenolate-bridged Pd/Pt complexes and allylpalladium complexes are of particular interest as both benzyl and allyl groups are known to cleave cleanly and thus would

provide a convenient way to prepare metal chalcogenides. Several benzylselenolate-bridged palladium and platinum complexes have been prepared (Scheme 5) and characterized. These complexes exist in *cis*- and *trans*-isomeric forms as shown by NMR spectroscopy¹².

Treatment of chloro-bridged allylpalladium dimer with $\text{Pb}(\text{ER})_2$ or $\text{Hg}(\text{TeR})_2$ in acetone affords organochalcogenolate bridged palladium complexes, $[\text{Pd}_2(\mu\text{-ER})_2(\eta^3\text{-allyl})_2]$ ^{27,28} (Scheme 6). The telluroato-bridged complex is unstable and decomposes at room temperature to Pd_3Te_2 (from XRD and Pd analysis) while thiolato- and selenolato-bridged complexes are stable but tend to darken with time and eventually become black. The NMR spectra of ER-bridged complexes indicate the presence of both *syn*- and *anti*-isomers in solution. In some cases, isomerization is slow on NMR time-scale to give separate resonances for two isomeric forms, while in others, the process is relatively rapid resulting in broad signals at room temperature. In such cases separate resonances can be observed at lower tem-

peratures²⁷. The X-ray structure of $[\text{Pd}_2(\mu\text{-SBu}^1)_2(\eta^3\text{-C}_4\text{H}_7)_2]$ revealed that the two palladium atoms are held to-

gether with two thiolato groups, while two allylic groups are mutually *syn*.

Thermal studies on methylallylpalladium complexes were undertaken²⁸. The thermogravimetric analyses revealed that the thiolato- and selenolato-bridged complexes decompose in three steps to give Pd₄E. Their decomposition in refluxing xylene proceeded smoothly to give Pd₄E (E = S or Se) as shown by XRD and Pd analysis. The SEM picture shows that these materials are microcrystalline in nature.

Trinuclear complexes

Three square planes of palladium(II) and platinum(II) in trinuclear complexes can be assembled in the following ways :

Scheme 7

Several trinuclear palladium(II) complexes stabilized with sulfido- or selenido-bridged [Pd₂(μ-E)₂{S₂P(OR)₂}]₂

Scheme 8

(PPh₃)₂] have been prepared (Scheme 7)²⁹.

The analytical and FAB mass spectral data are consistent with trinuclear formulation. In ¹H NMR spectra two sets of OR proton resonances in 1 : 1 ratio were observed. The ³¹P NMR spectra showed singlets for PPh₃ and S₂P(OR)₂. The ⁷⁷Se{¹H} NMR spectrum of [Pd₃(μ-Se)₂{S₂P(OPrⁿ)₂}(PPh₃)₂] exhibited a doublet at δ -98.7 ppm with ²J(Se-P)_{trans} 48 Hz. The molecular structure of [Pd₃(μ-S)₂{S₂P(OEt)₂}(PPh₃)₂], established by X-ray crystallography, consists of three distorted square-planar palladium atoms sharing two μ₃-S ligands²⁹. The TG analyses on several of these complexes were carried out. These complexes showed multiple fragmentation pattern finally leading to Pd₃ES (E = S or Se)³⁰.

The fragment '[Pd₂(μ-E)₂]' in the above molecules is analogous to [Pt₂(μ-S)₂L₄] (L = PPh₃, Ph₂pyP, ½dppf)³¹. The sulfur lone-pair in the latter molecules is sufficiently basic and can be compared with bidentate thioethers. Therefore, these molecules can function as a metallo-ligand. Thus

Fig. 7. ³¹P{¹H} and ¹⁹⁵Pt{¹H} NMR spectra of [Pt₂(μ-S)₂(Ptol₃)₄] in benzene-*d*₆

a soluble sulfido-bridged binuclear precursor, [Pt₂(μ-S)₂(Ptol₃)₄] has been prepared (Scheme 8). The NMR data are consistent to binuclear formulation (Fig. 7)³². The sulfido-bridged dimer can be used as a metallo-ligand. Accordingly, it reacts with several metal complexes to yield tri-, tetra- and high-nuclearity metal aggregates (Scheme 8). On coordination, the ³¹P NMR signal of [Pt₂(μ-S)₂(Ptol₃)₄] is shielded by ~10 ppm, whereas the magnitude of ¹J(Pt-P) increases by 178–418 Hz. The increase in ¹J(Pt-P) coupling constant indicates a diminished polarizability of the Pt-S bond as a consequence of the non-bonding electron-pair donation to the incoming metal atom.

The representative examples discussed here demonstrate that besides their fascinating chemistry, the low nuclearity organochalcogenolate complexes can serve both as precursors for advanced materials as well as excellent tectons for constructing large nuclearity structures. With time, the chemistry of organochalcogenolate complexes will gain further momentum in the solution of fundamental materials science problems.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Drs. J. P. Mittal and P. Raj for encouragement of this work. Stimulating collaborations with Dr. Babu Varghese, Dr. E. R. T. Tiekink, Dr. R. J. Butcher, Dr. R. Bohra and Dr. J. P. Jasinski are gratefully acknowledged.

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